

Online Workload Measurement Index for NPs: Study of Acceptability

Charlotte Mueller, PhD (c) ¹
Véronique Landry, PHCNP., PhD ²
Mira Jabbour, RD., MSc ³
André Daigle ²
Éric Tchouaket, PhD ⁴
Kelley Kilpatrick, RN., PhD⁵

1. University of Lucerne, Lucerne, Switzerland 2. University of Moncton, Moncton, New Brunswick, Canada
3. Centre intégré universitaire de santé et de services sociaux (CIUSSS) de l'Est-de-l'Île-de-Montréal—Hôpital
Maisonnette-Rosemont, Montréal, Québec, Canada 4. Université du Québec, Outaouais, Québec, Canada
5. McGill University, Montreal, Québec, Canada

Abstract

Aim: To examine the acceptability of using a workload measurement tool for nurse practitioners (NPs).

Background: There are important pressures in healthcare systems in Canada and internationally to increase the number of patients seen by healthcare providers in primary care, including NPs, as a strategy to increase care access. NPs work in various primary care settings, and with diverse patient populations. Previous research has found that patient, NP and organizational factors influence NP workload, with NPs utilizing both clinical and non-clinical activities to address patient care needs. However, we have a limited understanding of the factors that influence the acceptability and adequacy of measuring NP workload. Implementing an online NP workload measure in community-based primary care is complex.

Methods: Qualitative descriptive approach with individual semi-structured interviews ($n = 13$) with NPs and decision-makers. Data were collected from May–July 2024 in Québec, Canada. After a deductive coding strategy based on the Theoretical Framework of Acceptability, an inductive approach was used, to enable themes to emerge from the data. Interviews were coded individually by two researchers, and a third researcher reviewed the coding for consistency.

Findings: NPs and decision-makers ($n = 13$) reported that the workload measure was easy to use and comprehend. Participants believed the measure represented NPs' work, emphasizing that the recorded data enabled them to observe how their workload was spread among various activities. The tool's content and the brief data input time (five minutes per day) were perceived as facilitators of acceptability. A few minor obstacles were identified, including software issues, and recommendations were made for enhancements.

Conclusion: The study provides an in-depth understanding of the acceptability of using a workload measurement tool for NPs. Additional research is needed to explore the acceptability of implementing the tool of NP workload in other clinical areas, including mental health.

Keywords: *acceptability, nurse practitioner, online, primary care, qualitative descriptive study, workload measurement tool*

Introduction

Internationally and in the Canadian healthcare system, nurse practitioners (NPs) play a significant role in increasing access to care (Kilpatrick et al., 2024). NPs are registered nurses who have completed a master's degree. NPs can work autonomously to diagnose illnesses, as well as prescribe and manage medications, treatments, and diagnostic tests across a range of outpatient practice settings and patient populations (Ordre des infirmières et infirmiers du Québec, 2021). To gain a

more comprehensive understanding of NP roles and responsibilities, a useful approach is to measure their workload in different primary care settings (Kilpatrick et al., 2025).

Background

NPs in community-based primary care work in different settings, including home care, long-term care, and community health centers. Workload is measured by examining the time it takes to complete an activity (Kilpatrick et al., 2023; Muldoon et al.,

2012). Wide variability has been noted in NP workload (Housden et al., 2024). NP workload needs to be monitored to ensure the delivery of safe, high-quality care and reduce the risk of burnout for these providers (Kim et al., 2024).

Factors at the individual, organizational, and system levels influence NP workload and time spent on activities per patient (Martin-Misener et al., 2016; Landry & Kilpatrick, 2024). These factors must be taken into account in determining NP workload. Studies conducted in Québec and Ontario highlighted that not all NP tasks and activities are included in administrative databases (Kilpatrick et al., 2020; Rayner et al., 2020). Another challenge is that not all NPs are able to bill under their own name, making it difficult to measure NP activities (Slade et al., 2024). In our previous study (Kilpatrick et al., 2025), a static model of the tool was developed based on the findings from Landry and Kilpatrick (2024), the Nurse Practitioner Workload Index (NP-WI). The online version of the NP-WI is available in English and in French. Time spent in clinical (e.g., patient appointments) and non-clinical (e.g., teaching) role dimensions are specified. The NP-WI was pilot-tested from January–July 2024 with NPs and decision-makers/managers (n=69) within three health regions in Québec, Canada. NPs created a profile to document their individual characteristics (e.g., experience), primary and secondary work settings, and organizational characteristics (e.g., clerical or nursing support). Each day, NPs entered data into the NP-WI to identify patient appointment types and key patient characteristics (e.g., gender, age ≥ 65 years). Data in the NP-WI were collected over a total of 128 workdays, and data entry took five to seven minutes per day. In step 1 of the pilot study, we determined the feasibility and appropriateness of data entry (Kilpatrick et al., 2025). Given the complexity of measuring NP workload, it was important to examine the acceptability of using the online tool from the perspective of key interested groups. Acceptability, defined as perceptions of interested groups that an innovation or an intervention (online NP-WI), is: “[...] agreeable, palatable, or satisfactory” (Weiner et al., 2017). Decision-makers have very few validated tools to support NP workforce planning (Landry & Kilpatrick, 2024; World Health Organization, 2025) resulting in ad hoc implementation and wide variability in the number of patients seen by NPs in community-based primary care without a clear understanding of health system needs or the impact on patients and NPs (Kilpatrick et al., 2024, 2025; Martin-Misener et al., 2016) The aim of this study was to explore interested groups’ views of the acceptability of using the online NP-WI in their daily practice.

Conceptual Framework

The Theoretical Framework of Acceptability (TFA) outlines seven key constructs: 1) *Affective attitude* refers to how individuals feel about the NP-WI, including their emotional responses; 2) *Burden* is the perceived amount of effort required to participate in the measurement study; 3) *Ethicality* captures the extent to which the NP-WI aligns with an individual’s personal value system; 4) *Perceived effectiveness* reflects participants’ beliefs about whether the measurement study is likely to achieve its intended outcomes; 5) *Intervention coherence* concerns the extent to which participants understand the tool and its underlying mechanisms; 6) *Self-efficacy* denotes participants’ confidence in their ability to perform the behaviors required to engage in the study; 7) *Opportunity costs* refer to the extent to which taking part in the measurement study involves forgoing other benefits, resources, or valued activities (Sekhon et al., 2017).

Methods

Design

A qualitative descriptive study (Kim et al., 2016), supported by the TFA (Sekhon et al., 2017) framework, was used to explore the acceptability of the NP-WI. Semi-structured interviews gave interested groups (e.g., NPs, decision-makers/managers) an opportunity to express their personal views and experiences with the NP-WI. The manuscript follows the Standards for Reporting Qualitative Research (SRQR) (O’Brien et al., 2014).

Participants

NPs and decision-makers/managers who participated in step 1 of the pilot-test of the NP-WI were eligible to participate in this step. Decision-makers within the three health regions participated in this phase. Purposive sampling was used to recruit 13 participants with different levels of experience.

Data Collection

Semi-structured individual interviews were conducted from May–July 2024. Each participant completed a sociodemographic questionnaire with nine items (e.g., gender identity, age, role title, work experience [in years]). Individual interviews were conducted via phone by one co-author (M.J.). The questions for the semi-structured interview guide were developed based on the TFA framework. Interviews explored the participant’s experience using the tool, perceptions of burden, and adequacy of the tool’s content.

Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the Centre intégré universitaire de santé et de services sociaux (CIUSSS) de l'Est-de-l'Île-de-Montréal (approval #MP-12-2023-3358). The project was authorized by the RECs of the CIUSSS de la Capitale-Nationale (#MEO-12-2024-2852), CISSS de Lanaudière (#MEO-12-2024-133), CIUSSS de l'Ouest-de-l'Île-de-Montréal (MEO-12-2024-899) and the Université de Moncton (file #2324-032). Each participant completed an information and consent form, providing details about the research project. Participation was voluntary and participants could withdraw at any time. Data were aggregated by professional groups, and participants were given an alpha-numeric code.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were generated for sociodemographic data, collected through a questionnaire. The interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim by a professional transcriptionist. Content analysis was used for qualitative data (Bengtsson, 2016). Data analysis included a deductive coding approach based on the TFA, followed by an inductive approach to allow themes to emerge from the data (Sekhon et al., 2017). Two researchers (C.M., M.J.) coded the interviews individually, and a third researcher (K.K.) reviewed the coding for consistency. The primary deductive coding structure included 20 codes and was complemented by six additional codes that emerged from the data. The codes were categorized and synthesized into themes in the analysis (C.M., M.J., K.K.), and a total of 17 themes remained (see Table 2). The term “some” was applied when three to six participants discussed a theme, while “most” was used when seven to twelve participants mentioned the theme.

Findings

A total of 13 interviews were conducted over the telephone (Microsoft teams), lasting an average of 33 min 47 s (range =14–48 min). Sociodemographic characteristics of participants are displayed in Table 1. The majority were women (92.3%), NPs (76.9%) and had completed masters' level education (76.9%).

The themes are presented using the construction of the TFA Framework. Each code was assigned to one of the key constructs (See Table 2).

Affective attitude

Three codes were assigned to *affective attitude*. The first code *acceptability of the tool* is

defined as how easy the tool is to use and work with. Most participants reported they were satisfied with the acceptability and graphic representations in the tool. Participants mostly stated the tool was easy to use and understand, worked well, and was visually appealing. The tool was described as “*simple, user-friendly*” (NP 1), “*very intuitive, logical*” (Decision-maker/manager 6). One participant reported that it was easy to go back into the tool and add information. The second code *Representation* specifies if the tool is adequately showing the workload of NPs. Indicating an average number of patients per day gave most NPs a more profound understanding of their daily work. The tool content and its graphics were seen as helpful by NPs to organize their workdays as the clear distribution of clinical and non-clinical task provides insights into all components of their workday (NP 4; NP 5). One participant said, “*I think it actually allows us to dig a little deeper into everything that is part of NP practice because it's quite complex*” (Decision-maker/manager 9). Two participants reported that differences in setting, location, season, and patient population can influence workload. NPs noted that these differences in settings could be represented using the tool. A participant stated that the tool is a “*portrait of reality*” (NP 4). Another participant agreed, saying that the tool accounts for vacation time, training, or time away on leave (Decision-maker/manager 13). Participants are able to add socio-economic, financial and health factors to the tool to capture complex cases (patients in vulnerable situations) (NP 1). The participants were able to see the number of patients seen by NPs, including those who are not registered or rostered with them. The tool demonstrated a broader scope of practice from patient visits, monitoring test results and examinations, and follow-ups. Some participants reported that the tool helped them to identify problems in their work life, such as dissatisfaction or overworking (NP 8).

The third code *uncertainty about statistics* describes participants' perceptions towards their work data being presented through statistics. Participants described perceptions that ranged from feeling hesitant about how the instrument's results would be used to feeling very positive about the measure. Some participants were concerned about how the statistics could be viewed by decision-makers (NP 10) and healthcare professionals who did not know the extent of NP work. Participants wondered if they needed to justify their work or if the statistics could “backfire” (NP 7) on them if they did not meet expectations. Participants noted that the statistics only showed the average number of patients seen per day but did not provide an explanation of how they spent their time. For instance, other tasks performed

on a weekly basis like teaching with students or meetings are time-consuming but were not displayed (NP 1; NP 10; NP 11). A point of concern was the comparison between NPs and physicians (NP 9) if the information displayed in the measure was incomplete, as these highlighted differences in the number of patients seen per day without giving an explanation.

Burden

Burden included the codes *duration of data entry, case complexity, feedback on the tool, and software and hardware problems*. Participant feedback regarding the *duration of data entry* into the tool was mostly positive. Most participants needed five to a maximum of 10 minutes per day to enter data. NPs reported they learned quickly to enter their data throughout the day, rather than at the end of the day, to avoid feeling burdened (Decision-maker/manager 6). NPs shared that data entry “*wasn't very long*” (NP 12), “*not long to fill*” (Decision-maker/manager 13), and “*took a few minutes*” (NP 12).

Participants described how *case complexity* influence work and tool use. They explained that a complex case is a patient with several health issues (Decision-maker/manager 13). The tool was seen as helpful, as the “*number of issues*” and visual representation validated NP impressions (NP 10). Some participants found classifying patients difficult to do, particularly if patients did not exactly match the criteria or definitions for vulnerability. “*I'll give you an example. I have a colleague; her clientele is all very old. They are not vulnerable, but they are all very old.*” (Decision-maker/manager 13).

Participants indicated as *feedback on the tool* that the software and the tool were clearly explained by the research team. Some participants highlighted the importance of support from the research team regarding the teaching material (video, step-by-step guide, instructions), as well as training to use the measure (team meetings, training sessions, quick email responses to questions) (Decision-maker/manager 6, NP 10, NP 11). An initial training session lasted about 45 minutes. The research team explained the software with examples, which was very helpful, as were communications during the week. One participant stated, “*We were very well supported.*” (NP 4). The tool was perceived to have few barriers and was described as clear, simple, and intuitive, as well as suitable for an older generation or people who are not comfortable with technology (NP 7). The graphics, such as pie charts and diagrams, were visually appealing and had a good color scheme. Another participant stated they had the feeling that the tool was really built around NPs and

“*was really very well done and very useful*” (NP 10). The most frequently reported *software and hardware problems* were that participants were only able to save their entered data when all boxes were checked. This resulted in dissatisfaction for some participants, as they needed to search for the missing unchecked box. Similar challenges were noted if the date was not clicked at the top of the page. Some participants provided feedback on hardware problems with their computer, internet connections, and security settings on their work servers, and working in different settings hindered the use of the tool (e.g., clinic and long-term care or home care) (NP 2, NP 7, NP 10, NP 11, Decision-maker/manager 6).

Ethicality

The code *ethical context* defines whether the content of the tool aligns with the participants' values. Participants' main concern was the pressure to see more patients (NP 1) and being compared to physicians (NP 10). They worried about misinterpretations and a focus on the number of patients seen. One NP noted that if the NP is only seeing two patients a day, that could be interpreted as having an easier job with less work (NP 1). Participants highlighted the importance of having a trusting relationship with their decision-maker/manager. Some participants said in the past they avoided indicating too much administrative time and worked overtime to finish their work (NP 8). One participant stated that their dissatisfaction was caused by feeling overwhelmed by the amount of work and the number of additional patients they saw. With the tool, participants were able to capture their work in depth, which improved their time management regarding clinical and non-clinical tasks and allowed them to follow their work schedule better (NP 5).

Perceived effectiveness

Participants indicated that the *content of the tool* allowed them to see their workload as well as identify the learning curve of an NP. It displayed their individual time spent completing different activities within their role, including administrative activities, teaching, research, or in practice with patients. The NP-WI provided an overview of the patients NPs see, including patients they see in collaboration with other healthcare team members (e.g., nurses, other NPs, physicians), but who are not registered under their name (NP 5). The tool also revealed workload related to factors that contribute to longer appointments (e.g., home care). The tool allowed NPs to highlight if additional time was required to provide care to patients with complex needs. Different types of appointments required more or less time (Decision-maker/manager 13). Some participants stated that

there was some content missing regarding codes for “patients who were anxious or with mental health problems” and “patients with special needs” to better describe the clients in their practice (NP 8). With ‘adopting tool’, most participants responded that they would use the tool in the future. The tool provided valuable additional information, and it would be easy to integrate into their daily schedule (NP 10). One participant stated that filling out the tool represented another administrative task (NP 12).

Intervention coherence

Intervention coherence describes how well participants understand the intervention, including the following codes *item availability*, *item understanding* and *item improvements*.

Regarding *item availability*, some participants said they were aware that it was not possible to integrate all feedback and accommodate everyone’s requests because the setting, practices, and patient populations are diverse. One participant felt that “the categories that were there were very reasonable and representative” (NP 2). Another said that it is very helpful to be able to record the number of issues for every patient. Participants proposed small adjustments to improve the tool. These included a checkbox for circumstances that may prolong the appointment, such as a translator (language barrier) or having students (NP 1). A text box was requested for patients and the interprofessional team, as well as a checkbox for patients who did not show for their appointments (i.e., no-show) and a checkbox for NP vacation time (NP 4). Another suggestion was an extra field “other” including a checkbox for patients who do not fall into the vulnerable category. Some participants explained that the options were somewhat limited and needed to be modified over time.

Item understanding refers to how participants perceived terms and wording. For some, the term “vulnerable” was confusing and not well-defined (NP 1, NP 4). For example, people who “have housing instabilities or financial difficulties so they are not homeless, but they are very vulnerable and that’s not reflected” (NP 1). Another stated that it was not easy to rate how “satisfied” they were with their workload because other aspects than workload can influence their satisfaction. Participants suggested *improvements* including an option for the number of patients seen per hour or half-day to have a more accurate statistic. In addition to providing more graphics with detailed information about patient characteristics and the type of practice in the profile (Decision-maker/manager 9). Participants proposed connecting the tool with existing electronic health records to minimize data input time. Making data

accessible to NPs for longer periods of time could provide NPs a reflective tool to compare their practice over time. Another suggestion was to make the tool accessible for the profession of mental health NPs and to adjust it for mental health setting. (Decision-maker/manager 6)

Self-efficacy

Two codes, complexity of use and do-ability, were assigned to self-efficacy to understand if the participants can carry out the task of the tool. Participants reported to *Complexity of use* that it quickly became clear how to use the tool by entering the data. Some participants found filling the tool very doable in terms of time, workload, and simplicity (NP 1, NP 2). One participant said, “you know at the beginning there were always the little questions. Where do I put this?” (NP 12). This refers to cases that fit into more than one category, as the case contained parts of clinical and non-clinical tasks (NP 10). One participant stated that it can be a challenge to find the correct patients to enter missing data because for reasons of confidentiality there is no patient identification in the tool.

Opportunity costs

Participants commented on the code *time period of data collection* (four weeks; 20 days). Overall, most participants agreed that 20 workdays were sufficient to give an overall appreciation of their workload, and it was not demanding to do so. Four weeks worked well with the one-month work cycle, as in this cycle all important meetings were captured (NP 8). One participant stated that a two-week data collection period would have been too short (Decision-maker/manager 9). Another said that a longer period, up to 12 weeks, would give a more detailed representation regarding seasonal illnesses and influencing factors (extreme cases, maternity leave, vacation, spring break) (NP 4). The code *value* describes if the value of the tool matches the effort of the intervention. One participant stated that the extra time at the end of the day was worth it for a deeper understanding of the NP role and their practice (NP 2). Another said the time spent is very reasonable (NP 10).

Discussion

In the study, 13 NPs and decision-makers were interviewed about their experience completing the NP-WI. The NPs discussed their personal experiences with the NP-WI, including patient contact. Decision-makers reported on their experiences as managers and

Table 1. Sociodemographic Characteristics of Participants

Respondent Characteristics		Participants (<i>n</i> = 13)
Gender identity	Male	1
	Female	12
Age (in years)	Mean	43
	Range	30;58
Job position	Nurse Practitioner	10
	Decision-makers/managers	3
Education	Master's degree	10
	Specialty Certificate	3
Employment status	Full time	13
	Part-time	0
Licensed or registered in professional role (Mean in years)	Current role in this organization	7
	Working with this team	5

Table 2. Views of interested groups: Online NP Measurement Tool in community-based primary care

TFA Framework	Code	NP										Decision-makers/managers			
		P 1	P 2	P 3	P 4	P 5	P 7	P 8	P 10	P 11	P 12	P 6	P 9	P 13	
1. Affective attitude	Acceptability of the tool	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x
	Representation	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Uncertainty about statistics	x	x			x	x	x	x	x				x	x
2. Burden	Feedback to the tool	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Duration of entering data	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Case complexity	x	x			x		x	x	x					x
	Soft- / Hardware problems		x			x	x	x	x	x		x			x
3. Ethicality	Ethical context of tool	x				x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
4. Perceived effectiveness	Content of the tool	x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Adopting tool	x					x	x	x	x	x	x			x
5. Intervention coherence	Item availability	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
	Item Understanding	x			x			x	x		x				x
	Improvements	x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
6. Self-efficacy	Complexity of use	x			x	x		x	x	x	x				x
	Do ability	x	x		x				x				x		
7. Opportunity costs	Value		x						x		x				
	Time period of data collection	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

the feedback of the NPs under their supervision. Overall, the tool was viewed as practical and easy to use. The tool involves essential content and items that represent the NPs' workload in different community-based primary care settings,

including primary care, long-term care, and home care within the three health regions. The study highlights the close collaboration between the research team and participants in the practice sites that supported the successful pilot-test of the NP-WI.

Acceptability was explored after completing the first phase of implementation of the NP-WI. The seven components of the TFA supported all phases of the study.

Participants felt the NP-WI represented NP workload well. They reported that the tool displayed NPs scope of practice, including more complex elements of NP workload. Participants voiced their concerns about how other healthcare professionals could misinterpret lower numbers of patients seen in the contexts of home care, long-term care, patients with mental health issues, and those in vulnerable situations. The gap between actual workload and perceived workload is described in the study by Kapu et al. (2016), in which the perceived workload was lower than the actual workload, as non-clinical activities are often overlooked. The Kapu et al. study assessed workload factors of 1,466 advanced practice providers through a survey. The NP-WI is designed to distinguish between clinical and non-clinical activities to make the NP's role in patient care, teaching, or team meetings more visible. This highlights the importance of a more precise workload measurement tool for NPs.

Challenges have been examined when implementing online tools (e.g., electronic health records) to support practice and increase quality of care (Bosak & Thomsen, 2024). In the study of DeClerk et al. (2023) regarding the NP perspective on telehealth, key barriers, including technical problems, inadequate support from the organization, and a lack of technical expertise, were identified. Participants in our study stated that they felt well supported by the research team. Thus, only technical problems were identified as key barriers in working with the NP-WI, but the importance of supporting clinicians in the context of changes in practice was highlighted.

MacPhee et al. (2024) highlights that there is a clear need to develop and implement uniform workload measurement tools, as no standardized tools to measure NP workload exist.

Our study emphasized the number of patient health issues addressed in the health visit is an important component of a workload measurement tool. This type of holistic practice plays a significant role in how long the appointment takes and could be one additional factor that helps to distinguish between NP and physician practice. The study provides evidence that the NP-WI generates data to measure and describe the factors that influence NP workload at the patient, NP, organizational and system levels (Kilpatrick et al., 2025). Greater understanding of NP workload and the factors that influence NP workload in community-based primary

care can optimize NP role utilization and enhance access to care.

Implications for Research and Clinical Practice

The NP-WI tool is a first step to implement a health workforce information technology (Im, 2024) to measure NPs workload in community-based primary care settings. The tool lays the foundation to develop an infrastructure to gain insight into NP workload. Additional studies to scale up the use of the NP-WI are needed to identify the influence of patient, NP, organizational and system level factors on NP workload and care quality (Kilpatrick, Savard et al., 2024).

Future studies could adopt a value-based approach to examine NPs' holistic approach to care and the time spent to address several patient health issues within the same appointment. This could help to demonstrate how preventive measures and addressing underlying health issues could contribute to the overall quality of care, in addition to reducing adverse events for patients and costs for the healthcare system (Tchouaket et al., 2020). Presently, the instrument is implemented on a provincial scale; future research could focus on national and international assessments.

Limitations

The study was conducted in one Canadian province and cannot be generalized beyond this context. Participants were selected based on their experience working with the NP-WI.

Conclusions

NPs reported that the online NP Workload Index is easy to use and acceptable. The NP-WI takes five minutes to fill out each day. NPs and decision-makers/managers support the ongoing implementation of the NP-WI. Data from the NP-WI can be utilized to facilitate evidence-based workforce planning, cost analysis, and resource allocation. Additional research is needed to examine NP workload in different community-based primary care settings.

References

- Bengtsson, M. (2016). How to plan and perform qualitative study using content analysis. *NursingPlus Open*, 2, 8–14.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.npls.2016.01.001>

Bosak, K., & Thomsen, A. (2024). Implementation of an exercise prescription SmartPhrase in the electronic health record. *The Journal for Nurse Practitioners*, 21(1), Article 105261.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nurpra.2024.105261>

DeClerk, L., Wells, C., Chasteen, S., Baxter, J., Martinez, J., & Rojo, M. (2023). Preceptorship and telehealth: Nurse practitioners' perspectives. *The Journal for Nurse Practitioners*, 19(10), Article 104772. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nurpra.2023.104772>

Im, E. O. (2024). Health information technology and innovation in nursing knowledge generation. *Advances in Nursing Science*, 47(2), 121–122.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/ANS.0000000000000523>

Housden, L. M., Tantongco, M., Jiang, E., & Crowe, S. (2024). Optimizing patient care: A novel panel size calculator for primary care nurse practitioners. *Nurse Practitioner Open Journal*, 4(1), 329–468.

<https://doi.org/10.28984/npj.v1i1.468>

Kapu, A. N., McComiskey, C. A., Buckler, L., Derkazarian, J., Goda, T., Lofgren, M. A., McIlvennan, C. K., Raaum, J., Selig, P. M., Sicoutris, C., Todd, B., Turner, V., Card, E., & Wells, N. (2016). Advanced practice providers' perceptions of patient workload. *The Journal of Nursing Administration*, 46(10), 521–529.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/anna.0000000000000396>

Kilpatrick, K., Tchouaket, É., Jabbour, M., & Hains, S. (2020). A mixed methods quality improvement study to implement nurse practitioner roles and improve care for residents in long-term care facilities. *BMC Nursing*, 19(1), Article 6.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-019-0395-2>

Kilpatrick, K., Landry, V., Hakim, G. A., Jabbour, M., Ziegler, E., Rayner, J., Donald, F., Bryant-Lukosius, D., Martin-Misener, R., & Tchouaket, E. (2023). Predictors of time spent by nurse practitioners in primary care, home care, and long-term care on activities in two Canadian provinces: Time and motion studies. *Nurse Practitioner Open Journal*, 3(2), 66–79. <https://doi.org/10.28984/npj.v3i2.450>

Kilpatrick, K., Savard, I., Audet, L., Costanzo, G., Khan, M., Atallah, R., Jabbour, M., Zhou, W., Wheeler, K., Ladd, E., Gray, D. C., Henderson, C., Spies, L. A., McGrath, H., & Rogers, M. (2024). A global perspective of advanced practice nursing research: A review of systematic reviews. *PLOS ONE*, 19(7), Article e0305008.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0305008>

Kilpatrick, K., Landry, V., Tchouaket, E. N., Daigle, A., & Jabbour, M. (2025). Implementing an online instrument to measure nurse practitioner workload: A feasibility study. *Journal of Primary Care & Community Health*, 16, Article 21501319251321302.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/21501319251321302>

Kim, D. K., Scott, P., Poghosyan, L., & Martsolf, G. R. (2024). Burnout, job satisfaction, and turnover intention among primary care nurse practitioners with their own patient panels. *Nursing Outlook*, 72(4), Article 102190.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.outlook.2024.102190>

Kim, H., Sefcik, J. S., & Bradway, C. (2016). Characteristics of qualitative descriptive studies: A systematic review. *Research in Nursing & Health*, 40(1), 23–42. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.21768>

Landry, V., & Kilpatrick, K. (2024). Essential elements of a workload measurement instrument for nurse practitioners. *The Journal for Nurse Practitioners*, 20(10), Article 105214.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nurpra.2024.105214>

MacPhee, M., Havaei, F., Bookey-Bassett, S., Neumann, W. P., Qureshi, S., Greig, M., & Keselman, D. (2024). Commentary on the past, present, and future of nursing workload research. *Nursing Research and Reviews*, 14, 59–67.

<https://doi.org/10.2147/nrr.s442571>

Martin-Misener, R., Kilpatrick, K., Donald, F., Bryant-Lukosius, D., Rayner, J., Valaitis, R., Carter, N., Miller, P. A., Landry, V., Harbman, P., Charbonneau-Smith, R., McKinlay, R. J., Ziegler, E., Boesveld, S., & Lamb, A. (2016). Nurse practitioner caseload in primary health care: Scoping review.

International Journal of Nursing Studies, 62, 170–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2016.07.019>

Muldoon, L., Dahrouge, S., Russell, G., Hogg, W., & Ward, N. (2012). How many patients should a family physician have? Factors to consider in answering a deceptively simple question. *Healthcare Policy*, 7(4), 26–34. <https://doi.org/10.12927/hcpol.2013.22885>

O'Brien, B. C., Harris, I. B., Beckman, T. J., Reed, D. A., & Cook, D. A. (2014). Standards for reporting qualitative research. *Academic Medicine*, 89(9), 1245–1251.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/acm.0000000000000388>

Ordre des infirmières et infirmiers du Québec. (2021, February 19). *Specialized nurse practitioners and*

their practice: Guidelines (Information Note 2530).
<https://www.oiiq.org/documents/20147/2943833/2530-np-guidelines-web.pdf>

Rayner, J., Donald, F., Martin-Misener, R., Glazier, R. & Kopp, A. (2020). Nurse practitioner activities in Ontario family health teams comparing three different data sources. *Nursing Leadership*, 33(2), 67–79. <https://doi.org/10.12927/cjnl.2020.26236>

Sekhon, M., Cartwright, M., & Francis, J. J. (2017). Acceptability of healthcare interventions: An overview of reviews and development of a theoretical framework. *BMC Health Services Research*, 17(1), Article 88. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-017-2031-8>

Slade, E. P., DePriest, K., Commodore-Mensah, Y., Samuel, L., Hanson, G. C., & D'Aoust, R. (2024). State full practice authority regulations and nurse practitioner practice autonomy: Evidence from the 2018 National Sample Survey of Registered Nurses. *Medical Care Research and Review*, 82(1), 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10775587241282163>

Tchouaket, É., Kilpatrick, K., & Jabbour, M. (2020). Effectiveness for introducing nurse practitioners in six long-term care facilities in Québec, Canada: A cost-savings analysis. *Nursing Outlook*, 68(5), 611–625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.outlook.2020.06.002>

Weiner, B. J., Lewis, C. C., Stanick, C., Powell, B. J., Dorsey, C. N., Clary, A. S., Boynton, M. H., & Halko, H. (2017). Psychometric assessment of three newly developed implementation outcome measures. *Implementation Science*, 12(1), Article 108. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-017-0635-3>

World Health Organization (2025). State of the world's nursing 2025: investing in education, jobs, leadership and service delivery. *World Health Organization*.
<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240110236>